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Fiscal Management Practices of Public Schools: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

This study assessed the systematic review of the publish papers between 2019-2024 about the practices of fiscal management in public schools. It answered the concerns on the practice of fiscal management in public schools in areas of planning, then review and approval, implementations, monitoring, evaluation, and then communication. It also compared the assessment on fiscal practices of the studies from different countries. The findings revealed that the fiscal management practices by public schools is absolutely evident in budget planning, then review and approval, implementations, monitoring, evaluation, and then communication as observed by teachers, parents, and community leaders. Among the twelve papers published between 2019-2024, three share common financial management practices: planning, then review and approval, implementations, monitoring, evaluation, and then communication. However, school administrators from different countries exhibited varied practices of fiscal transparency.

Keywords: *fiscal management practices, public schools, systematic review*

Introduction

The demands for fiscal transparency from the government all over the world is gaining great push by some important institutions and organizations like as Fund (IMF), Transparency International (TI), the World Bank, and the likes. The Philippines being one of the countries that submitted to such a cause, has been doing its part to conform with the IMF's Code of Good Practices on Fiscal Management. Data from TI reveal that gradually, the Philippines is gaining good results based on its Corruption Perception Index (CPI) of 2.4 in 2009 to 2.8 in 2014, or from 139th to 85th of the 180 participating countries being the 180th as the most corrupt.

This status of becoming more transparent in the global perspective has been cascaded to national government agencies (NGAs) through laws. Among these laws is Republic Act (R.A) 10155 or General Appropriation Act (GAA) FY 2012 wherein Sec. 93 requires agencies concerned to establish and maintain a Transparency Seal on their websites. It contains vital information about the agency as its mandates and functions, accountable persons, annual reports, approved budget for the current year and the corresponding targets, status of implementation of its programs and its annual procurement plan.

The Department of Education (DepEd) has complied with this and even made more initiatives to promote fiscal transparency to its smaller units particularly in schools and learning centers. Regional and Division Memoranda have been issued to public schools. Both offices require schools to establish a Transparency Board to show to the public how much revenues do schools annually have and how these funds are being spent. School revenues including Maintenance and Other Operating expenses (MOOE), Special Education Funds (SEF), parent- Teachers Association (PTA) funds, proceeds from school canteen and other fundraising drives, organizational (Math, Science, English, etc.) funds and donations from different sources.

Research Objective

The systematic review specifically aims to answer the following objective:

1. To determine fiscal management practices of public schools.

Literature Review

According to Kopits and Craig (1998) fiscal management on actions, rules, plans, and processes in a relevant, timely, accessible, and accurate manner is important for fiscal transparency. Openness regarding operations of the government, intentions of fiscal policies, public sector financial records and forecasts is important. Their ideas of management confirmed to the International Monetary Fund (IMF) Code of Fiscal Management (IMF) (2007) which were categorized into areas of practices: 1) clear definition responsibilities; 2) transparent budget procedures; 3) accessible public information; and 4) promises of information integrity, with external verification necessity.

In the same manner, Baldrich (2005) disclosed that fiscal management clearly outlines the government's roles and responsibilities, provides to the public, openly creates and implements the budget, and ensures the integrity of fiscal processes. He claimed that accountability in the public is the trademark of fiscal management. Transparent budgets, easily accessible to the public and policymakers, provide consolidated information (Poterba and von Hagen, 1999).

Management and transparency are being advocated globally in different countries, in the Philippines as one of the democratic countries, it is regarded as one of the principles along with accountability in the attainment of good governance. Among its legal bases include the section 7 of 1987 Philippine Constitution which states that "The right of the people to information on matters of public concern shall be recognized. Access to official records, and to documents and papers pertaining to official acts, transactions, or decisions, as

well as to government research data used as basis for policy development, shall be afforded the citizen, subject to such limitations as may be provided by law”.

The ideas and concept about fiscal transparency as well as some of its legal bases provided the researcher a clearer view and basis in assessing the fiscal transparency practices of public secondary school administrators. Although, almost all of the ideas and concepts cited above are drawn in an international perspective, their applicability to the local setting such as school holds true and is very feasible. Its legal bases provide a compelling force to accountable persons to exhibit and practice the said principle of good governance along with accountability for the betterment of the people or stakeholders.

Fiscal Management

Funding and a budget are essential elements of management. These are important since these enable the leaders the ability to manage and control the financial fund sources needed in order to sustain implementation of various initiatives and programs that best support the growth of the educational institution. (Omokorede, 2011).

To ensure effective financial resource management, school administrators should possess sufficient understanding on financial management. The effectiveness in a school's financial management can make all the difference in its success. Effective money management guarantees that resources at the school are efficiently utilized to carry out the objective of the institution and achievement goal (Harvey, 2014).

Fiscal management in public schools is the performance of management actions connected with the financial wellbeing of a school for the achievement of efficient education (Joubert and Bray 2007). Bisschoff (2007) describes school financial management as as the act of guaranteeing that the school's governing body and management team effectively manage the funds in order to reach the school's objectives. Effective education is achieved properly by schools through essential financial management. It is essential for principles to secure accountability and prudence in the utilization of school funds Kaguri, Njatti, and Thianine (2014).

Acknowledging the actions of leaders, especially in the public sector, are a crucial and important matter. Actually, public sector executives play a crucial part in reaching high levels of key components of good governance (Elmasry and Bakri 2019). Additionally, fiscal transparency educates the public how tax and government money are allocated. This is an essential component of efficient public finance oversight. Transparency gives people a peek into public spending plans and aids in holding governments responsible. It helps market growth, self-assurance and durability.

Methodology

Research Design

The systematic review process was used in order to synthesize the data on fiscal transparency practices of public schools. The methodology followed the Sandelowski and Barroso's approach (2007), which then was utilized in the research of Recla and Potane (2024) on teachers' practices and challenges in managing multigrade level classes. This design consisted of three steps: (1) selecting published papers, (2) review of quality and extraction of data, and (3) summarizing and synthesizing.

Instrument

A roster of published papers with citations on public schools was generated by Publish or Perish software via the Google Scholar. All studies that were published, with citations between 2019 and 2024 that were related and relevant to this study were reviewed. Publish or Perish was employed terms such as “fiscal management”, and “school”. The results of Publish and Perish were assessed for quality using the Literature Matrix template and

Programme (CASP). The studies and researches were carefully evaluated using the CASP to assess the design of the study, sampling methods, data collection means, and analysis techniques in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) Guidelines to guarantee inclusion in all pertinent information.

Data Analysis

Thematic analysis conducted by Cana et al. (2023) was used to compare studies following protocols established by Clark and Braun (2017), which were then utilized to analyze and investigate the data on teachers' experiences with multigrade classrooms. This study was modified using a six-step process of thematic analysis, involving: (1) examining relevant studies to identify themes, (2) assigning categories based on information unique to each category, (3) gathering relevant data in order to define themes, (4) creating a map to review the themes, (5) categorizing and explaining the themes to clearly outline the themes, and last, (6) enhancing the result report by discussing the analysis and recommendations.

Results and Discussion

Search Results

The final group of 12 papers identified involved various studies.

Figure 1. Results of search conducted in screening the papers to be included in systematic review.

By the usage of the PRISMA Flow Chart, 3 stages were taken in selecting the research papers, which were: (1) identification, (2) screening, and (3) inclusion. During the identification stage, the 200 studies in Google Scholar were a part of initial stage in the screening process by using Publish or Perish. There were following papers that were eliminated: 158 because the titles were not related to the study and 3 because of the unavailability of sources, leaving a total of 39. On the second stage, screening, 10 papers were removed because the abstracts were irrelevant to its corresponding research questions, 8 because of the unavailability of the full papers, and 6 because they were unable to match the criteria using the CASP checklist, which then resulted in a final of 12 studies.

The 12 studies produced 5 themes, namely: the planning, then review and approval, followed by implementation, then monitoring and evaluation, and communication.

Theme 1: Planning

Based on the systematic review, there were 4 (four) papers that practice “planning” in fiscal management. From these 4 our studies, 2 studies were from Nigeria that were published in 2020, and 2022, 2 papers were from the Philippines and published in 2021, and 2022. 3 studies used a descriptive research design and 1 used a mixed method. Hence, all studies shared the same concept of planning in fiscal management.

Planning is a very essential part of an effective school fiscal management (Du Preez et al. 2019). The initial phase of the budgeting process is the most transparent, providing ample opportunities for public participation. During this phase, the budget typically mirrors the school's organizational hierarchy by subdividing the school's activities into separate parts or groups. It also examines how these components can be organized to establish and sustain high-quality learning experiences.

On the other note, Brillantes & Soco (2015) refer to participatory planning and budgeting involves citizens in identifying local priorities, policies, programs, and projects that need resources allocated. With their active participation, citizens can therefore commit to support and do their share in realizing those policies, programs, and projects.

Theme 2: Review and Approval

From the reviewed papers about fiscal management, there is no study that practices review and approval as (Palmes 2016), review and approval are done after the planning stage where consensus of the group about the annual budget has been arrived, another conference shall be called for the school planning team to convene for the finalization of the budget document. The said conference will give an opportunity to each member of the planning team for necessary inclusion, revision and / or deletion of item/s after an ample time of studying and reviewing the drafted budget document.

Review and Approval procedure is essential to guaranteeing financial transparency in public secondary schools. Reviewing and approving the budget signals a shift from broad and flexible planning procedures to stricter and internal execution procedures. This part of the procedure is characterized by being more mechanistic and inward compared to the initial stage. Finance staff and officials

collaborate to develop an official financial report that mirrors the priorities established during the planning procedure. The formal budget must also adhere to legal regulations of the Department of Education laws.

The approval stage follows, where final authorization is granted by the appropriate authority, such as the school board or a governing financial body. This dual process of review and approval not only helps in identifying and rectifying any discrepancies but also fosters a culture of accountability and transparency. By involving various levels of oversight, schools can be assured that the financial resources were managed prudently, ethically, ultimately supporting effective and transparent fiscal governance.

The study entitled "Internal Control Systems on Financial Accountability in National Public Secondary Schools in Kenya" by Atieno and Kiganda (2020) on the effectiveness of internal control systems towards financial accountability within Kenyan national public secondary schools. The study has five main goals: to investigate how control actions, information and then communication, assessment on risk, environment control, and monitoring affect financial accountability. The data were collected from 103 schools using the audited financial documents and questionnaires using a descriptive survey design. The study discovered that these control aspects had a substantial combined impact on financial accountability.

Another study posits that the relationship between financial resource management and academic outcomes for students in secondary schools in Kaduna State, Nigeria is examined study "Impact of Financial Resource Management on Students' Academic Performance in Secondary Schools in Kaduna State, Nigeria" by Imam (2022). The study sampled 559 participants, including administrators, teachers, and supervisors, using a descriptive survey approach. Data were then gathered by using a questionnaire, and a Cronbach Alpha score of 0.84 indicated the instrument's reliability. The study used ANOVA to test hypotheses, then mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions. The findings showed that the students' academic performance is highly impacted by efficient financial resource management. In particular, it has been discovered that prudent financial management and budgetary adherence have a favorable impact on academic results. As per the study's findings, the Kaduna State Government ought to guarantee periodic audits to foster accountability and openness in the administration of financial resources. It also emphasized the necessity of having a variety of financing sources to support educational projects and activities, such as donations from philanthropists, non-governmental organizations, and parent organizations. The findings highlight how important financial resources are to raising educational standards and accomplishing more ambitious educational objectives in Nigeria.

Theme 3: Implementation

Robert, Charles, and Aisha (2021) conduct a systematic study on the management of financial sources for school development and improvement in Uganda. The study acknowledges the vital role played by financial management in ensuring quality education in an institution. The sources of financing are identified as well as the roles that both government and parents take in providing for education. This assessment highlights the significance of maximizing these provisions through strategic deployment, allocation, procurement, and maintenance for specific learning objectives namely better infrastructure facilities, instructional materials etc. Despite certain challenges such as inadequate parental contributions or minimal government funding, it promotes better financial management models that are globally grounded.

In other words, schools can achieve their goals even with different levels of funding if they focus on key subjects that support national socioeconomic aspirations. In particular, it argues that there is a need for a strong regulatory framework which should be supported by various legislative measures to govern the use of Ugandan school money (Accounting website). Boards of Directors have the overall responsibility to ensure transparency is adhered to while qualified accountants keep good books records in order to increase demand and encourage innovation that is in line with societal demands. With the goal of promoting school growth and improvement, this all-encompassing strategy makes financial management a crucial component of a successful education in Uganda.

Theme 4: Monitoring and Evaluation

Based on the systematic review, there were two studies that one of the practices of Fiscal Management is the Monitoring and Evaluating. These studies are from Atieno and Kiganda (2020) of Kenya, and Ayeni (2020) of Nigeria. The study investigated the principal's instructional supervision time management strategies, teachers' efficacy in instructional supervision tasks, and then on the academic performance of the students. The other one is to evaluate the effects of the internal control systems towards the financial accountability in the national public secondary schools in Kenya. Both studies used descriptive survey as research design.

From their study, monitoring is defined as ensuring that the structures are carrying out activities, which is intended, involves conducting periodic or regular assessments (Moraa, 2015). These evaluations help determine if the other components of internal control continues to operate according to plan. Furthermore, these assessments aid in documenting internal control weaknesses and passing them on to appropriate personnel responsible for taking supervised action.

Furthermore, the monitoring and the evaluation is an important managerial tool to track down the progress and facilitate in the decision making process. It provides review and assessment of the progress towards objectives, identifies problems and strategies, and makes adjustments to plans. Monitoring and evaluating the expenditure of funds are very necessary actions to determine whether school funds were spent properly and accordingly as well as to determine efficiency and effectiveness of a certain program, project or activities where the funds were spent.

Theme 5: Communication

Based on the systematic review, there were three studies that practice communication in terms of Fiscal Management. These studies are from Atieno and Kiganda (2020) of Kenya, Ayeni (2020) of Nigeria, and Brown and Adooh (2021). The study investigated on the principal's instruction time management and performance strategies, teachers' efficacy on instructional supervision tasks, and the academic performance of the students. The other one is evaluating the efficacy of internal control systems towards the financial accountability in public secondary schools in Kenya. Both studies used the descriptive survey as a research design. While the other study of Brown and Adooh (2021) discussed several aspects of research methods focusing on managing the fiscal accountability in the public schools.

According to Bockh and Blakeslee (2017) effective communication is crucial during the budgeting process. The budget documents, along with the hearings, justifications, and other components of the process, serve as a means of communication. Every activity consists of a communication component, which can be written or spoken. The success of the agency and its operating components in obtaining resources depends on what is communicated and how it is communicated. Communicating the outcomes of resource utilization is just as crucial as the commitments made during the resource acquisition process.

Furthermore, COSO (2013) defines that communication is a recurring and iterative process of providing, distributing and getting the necessary information. It is how data is spread out towards the organization, moving upwards, downwards and sideways. This helps the employees to receive clear messages from their senior management on the need of serious attention given to control tasks. With regards to external communication it has two dimensions: inbound messages about important external developments and provision of information to outsiders in response to their demands and opportunities.

Conclusions

In light of below conclusion were drawn:

Three of the twelve published papers between 2019-2024 share the same financial management practices. These practices include the planning, then review and approval, followed by implementation, then monitoring and evaluation, and communication.

The public school administrators implemented the practices on fiscal transparency as absolutely evident, they were able to demonstrate the mandate on fiscal transparency in the five areas of fiscal management such as the planning, then review and approval, followed by implementation, then monitoring and evaluation, and communication.

Based on the findings and the conclusions of the study, these following recommendations were made:

The school leaders must create and innovate programs that would strengthen and develop leadership skills, confidence and feeling of empowerment towards the students towards meaningful and purposeful participation in the financial and school management.

The school leaders must post the approved budget and provide each School-Community Planning Team (SPT) member a copy of the approved budget for monitoring and evaluation purposes.

The school leaders must sustain the use of the transparency board and regularly update its entries to keep the stakeholders informed of the status of school funds.

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